

30 min at 100° and this method of Harborne⁷ was employed for the quantitative estimation of aglycones and sugars.

Acid hydrolysis⁸ of flavonol glycoside gave myricetin, L-rhamnose and D-glucose. The behaviour of peaks at 258, 268 and 357 nm in its uv spectra, in the presence of NaOAc, NaOMe and AlCl₃ was in agreement with those of myricetin-3-O-glucoside-7-O-rhamnoside or myricetin-7-O-glucoside-3-O-rhamnoside; thus indicating the absence of free phenolic group at C-3 and C-7. Flavonol glycoside was treated with acetic anhydride and pyridine at room temperature to give the acetylated product. The ¹H nmr (90 MHz; CCl₄) spectrum of acetylated derivative showed signals at δ 1.9–2.25 (4H, s, 1 × acetate-CH₃), 0.92–1.35 (6H, unresolved-d, 2 × rhamnose-CH₃), 3.45 (2H, s, rhamnose/glucose-C-1-H), at 3.65–3.97 (2H, diffused-q, rhamnose-C-5-H), 4.1–4.4 and 4.9–5.45 (20H, m, primary and secondary H of glucose/rhamnose), doublet and multiplet at 6.7 (1H, J 3 Hz, Ar-6-H), 7.03 (1H, J 3 Hz, Ar-8-H) and 7.4–7.8 (2H, Ar-2', 6'-H). The glycosylation of 7-hydroxyl group was supported by downfield shift⁹ in pmr spectra (indicated by signals at δ 6.70 (d, 6-H) and 7.03 (d, 8-H) to shift downfield). Moreover, in ¹H nmr (90 MHz, CDCl₃) spectra of silylated flavonolglycoside, the sugar region showed signals at δ 1.15 (6H, d, J 6.5 Hz, 2 × rhamnose-CH₃), 4.5–5.1 (2H, m, rhamnose/glucose-C-1-H), 2.9–4.2 (20H, m, primary and secondary-H of glucose/rhamnose), and doublets at 6.27, 6.75, 7.1 and 7.92 (1H each, J 9.0 Hz each, Ar-2', 6', 6, 8-H).

Mass spectral fragments¹⁰ m/z 450, 362 (terminal glucose, rhamnose), 378, 289 (internal glucose, rhamnose), 590 ((aglycone + H) – 15) and 740, 651 (1→2, interglycosidic linkage) and ¹H nmr spectra (TMS ether)⁸ of flavonol glycoside and its acetyl derivative confirmed that parent glucoside contained two rhamnose and two glucose units; m/z (rel intensity %) 740 (0.5), 651 (0.5), 590 (0.6), 502 (0.8), 487 (4.1), 450 (3.3), 430 (8.2), 415 (6.5), 378 (1.6), 363 (4.1), 362 (3.3), 361 (9.0), 289 (6.5), 273 (2.5), 217 (23.8), 204 (19.7), 191 (4.9), 169 (4.9), 157 (6.5), 147 (22.9), 129 (18.0), 117 (12.3), 103 (19.7), 85 (4.9), 75 (31.1), 74 (13.1) and 73 (100). Therefore, the structure of flavonol tetraglycoside might be either 3-O-(2-rhamnosylglucosyl)-7-O-β-glucosylrhamnosylmyricetin or 3-O-(2-glucosylrhamnosyl)-7-O-β-rhamnosylglucosylmyricetin.

The position of the glucosidic and 3-O-(2-rhamnosylglucosyl) or glucosidic and 3-O-(2-glucosylrhamnosyl) was determined by enzymatic hydrolysis⁸ of flavonol tetraglycoside with β-glucosidase, which supported the latter, i.e. 3-O-(2-glucosylrhamnosyl)-7-O-β-(2-rhamnosylglucosyl)myricetin; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 725, 1 045 (OCOCH₃), 1 600, 1 430, 1 370 (C=C), 1 760, 1 135, 1 080 (C=CCO) and 2 920 cm⁻¹ (CH); λ_{max} (methanol) 257, 359; (+NaOCH₃) 271, 400; (+AlCl₃) 276, 435; (+AlCl₃ - HCl) 270, 406; (+CH₃COONa) 260, 382; and (+CH₃COONa +

H₂BO₃) 259, 376 nm; λ_{max} (hydrolysed; methanol) 257, 374; (+NaOCH₃) 274, 452; (+AlCl₃) 256, 310 (sh), 372 (sh), 452; (+AlCl₃ - HCl) 257, 423; and (+CH₃COONa) 258, 420 nm.

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Chemical Constituents of the Orchid *Dendrobium farmerii*: Further Evidence for the Revised Structure of Dengibsin

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WE reported earlier^{1-4,6-28} a number of compounds from a series of Indian orchids. These compounds represent several structural types, such as bibenzyls¹⁻³, phenanthrenes⁴⁻¹¹ (both monomeric and dimeric), phenanthropyrans¹² and pyrones¹³, 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes¹⁴⁻¹⁶ (both monomeric and dimeric), 9,10-dihydrophenanthropyrans¹⁷⁻²³ and pyrones^{13,17-19,23}, simple aromatic compounds²⁴, triterpenoids^{25,26} and steroids^{27,28}. As part of this general programme of research we have chemically investigated yet another new Indian orchid *Dendrobium farmerii* which has afforded the fluorenone derivative dengibsin (2a), two coumarin derivatives ayapin and aesculatin dimethyl ether and *p*-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid. These compounds were characterised

NOTES

by their spectroscopical data and in some cases by direct comparison with authentic samples.

- 1a ; R₁=R₂=OH, R₃=H, R₄=OMe
- 1b ; R₁=R₂=OAc, R₃=H, R₄=OMe
- 2a ; R₁=H, R₂=R₄=OH, R₃=OMe
- 2b ; R₁=H, R₂=R₄=OAc, R₃=OMe
- 3 ; R₁=R₂=R₃=R₄=H

Dengibsin, earlier isolated by Talapatra *et al.*²⁹ from a taxonomically related orchid *Dendrobium gibsonii*, was initially assigned the structure 1a on the basis of uv, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data. The structure of dengibsin was later revised as 2a independently by themselves³⁰ from reexamination of these spectral data, and by Sargent³¹ by its total synthesis. We present in this paper additional

TABLE 1 - ¹³C CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF DENGIBSIN DIACETATE (2b) AND FLUORENONE (3)

Carbon atoms	Chemical shifts (δ values) ^a	
	2b	3
C-1	110.69	124.08
C-2	152.7	128.86
C-3	112.26	134.47
C-4	154.89	120.12
C-4a	126.96	144.21
C-4b	136.72 ^b	144.21
C-5	144.80	120.12
C-6	130.40	134.47
C-7	129.56	128.86
C-8	122.21	124.08
C-8a	136.01 ^b	133.97
C-9	191.72	193.50
C-9 ^a	135.35 ^b	133.97
OAc	168.77	-
	168.97	-
	20.96	-
	21.0	-
OMe	56.66	-

^a Values are in ppm downfield from TMS : ^δTMS = ^δCDCl₃ + 76.9 ppm.

^b Values are interchangeable.

Fig 1. HETCOR 2D contour plot of dengibsin diacetate (2b) showing 1-bond CH correlations.

evidence in support of the revised structure 2a derived from ^{13}C and 2D-nmr spectral analysis of dengibsin diacetate (2b). The δ_c values of dengibsin diacetate (Table 1) was assigned by comparison with the carbon chemical shifts of fluorenone (3) recorded independently by us. The degree of protonation of each carbon atom in both the compounds was determined by APT experiments. Confirmation of the δ_c values of the protonated carbon atoms was made by 1-bond heteronuclear correlation plot ($^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}$) (Fig. 1) obtained from a HETCOR 2D experiment of dengibsin diacetate using J_{CH} parameter of 160 Hz. A long-range (3-bond) HETCOR experiment of this compound was, however, not very successful presumably because of the relatively high T_1 values of the quaternary carbon atoms of this type of compounds. The most upfield *meta*-coupled aromatic proton of dengibsin diacetate at δ 6.76 which can be readily identified to be due to H-3 showed a strong 1-bond correlation with the carbon resonance at δ_c 112.36. The latter must then be attributed to C-3 of dengibsin diacetate. The counterpart of the above *meta*-coupled aromatic proton must be H-1 which, in turn, exhibited a similar strong 1-bond correlation with the carbon atom resonating at δ_c 110.79. This should, therefore, be assigned to C-1. The chemical shifts of C-1 (δ_c 110.79), C-3 (δ_c 112.36) and C-4a (δ_c 126.96) of dengibsin diacetate when compared with the δ_c values of the corresponding carbon atoms of parent fluorenone, are consistent with the revised structure 2b with the methoxyl group at C-4 and one of the acetoxy functions at C-2. With the earlier formulation 1b having these groups interchanged, C-1 would have shifted to a more upfield position and C-4a would not have suffered so much upfield shift compared with the corresponding carbon atoms of parent fluorenone. The placement of the remaining acetoxy function of dengibsin diacetate at C-5 rather than at C-8 position was confirmed by the following facts. C-8a and C-9a of dengibsin diacetate appeared essentially at the same position as the corresponding carbon atoms of parent fluorenone (δ_c 133.97). An acetoxy group at C-8 of dengibsin diacetate would have caused an upfield shift of its C-8a by $\sim$ 6 ppm. The observation that with the exception of C-4a (δ_c 126.96) no other quaternary carbon of dengibsin diacetate resonated at a field higher than that of C-8a (δ_c 133.97) of fluorenone ruled out the placement of an acetoxy function at C-8. The chemical shifts and splitting patterns of the remaining aromatic protons of the compound left the only option for this acetoxy function to be at C-5. The ^1H nmr signals at δ 7.10, 7.28 and 7.50 could then be assigned to H-6, H-7 and H-8, respectively. The downfield shift of H-3 is consistent with its being *peri* to the fluorenone carbonyl function. The above ^1H nmr signals showed strong 1-bond correlations with the carbon resonances at δ_c 130.40, 129.56 and 122.21 respectively,

which should, therefore, correspond to C-6, C-7 and C-8, respectively, of dengibsin diacetate. The relatively upfield shifts of C-4b and C-6 (both *ortho* to a 5-acetoxy function) and that of C-3 (*para* to 5-acetoxy function) of dengibsin diacetate compared with the corresponding carbon atoms of parent fluorenone further affirmed the placement of the second acetoxy function at C-5 in the former. The C-7, being *meta* to the above acetoxy function, showed only a marginal downfield shift.

The above spectral data thus unequivocally established the revised structure 2b for dengibsin diacetate, and hence 2a for dengibsin itself.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Kofler Block and are uncorrected ^1H nmr spectra were recorded on 80 MHz Varian CFT-20 instrument with TMS as internal standard. ^{13}C and 2D nmr were run on a Varian XL-400 spectrometer. Mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV using a direct inlet system and the figures in the first bracket attached to each m/z values indicate relative intensity of peaks. Silica gel (60-100 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc. The purity of the samples was tested by tlc and MS. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic solvents and petrol used had b.p. 60-80°.

Isolation of dengibsin (2a), ayapin, aesculatin dimethyl ether and p-hydroxyphenyl propionic acid: Air-dried powdered whole plant of *D. farmerii* (1 kg) was kept soaked with EtOH at room temperature for 3 weeks. The ethanolic extract was then drained out and concentrated under reduced pressure to about 100 ml, diluted with water (500 ml) and exhaustively extracted with Et_2O . The extract was fractionated into acidic and neutral parts by treatment with 2M aqueous NaOH. The alkaline solution was acidified in the cold with concentrated HCl and the liberated solid was again extracted with Et_2O , washed, dried and the solvent removed. The residue was chromatographed. The early fractions of the petrol-EtOAc (10:1) eluate on evaporation gave ayapin (0.5 g), crystallised from petrol-EtOAc, m.p. 230°; ^1H nmr δ 6.06 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.26 (1H, d, J 9.6 Hz, H-3), 6.82 (2H, s, H-5 and H-8) and 7.57 (1H, d, J 9.6 Hz, H-4); m/z 190 (M^+ , 100), 162 (55), 161 (45), 79 (10) and 76 (15). The later fractions of the same eluate afforded aesculatin dimethyl ether (0.2 g), crystallised from the same solvent mixture, m.p. 144°; ^1H nmr δ 3.92 and 3.95 (each 3H, s, ArOCH_2), 6.28 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-3), 6.85 (2H, s, H-5 and H-8) and 7.58 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-4); m/z 206 (M^+ , 100), 191 (44), 178 (14), 163 (27), 135 (16), 107 (14), 79 (14) and 69 (16).

Elution of the above column with petrol-EtOAc (5:1) gave *p*-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid (0.05 g), crystallised from the same solvent mixture,

m.p. 122°. The identity of the compound was established by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Further elution of the column with petrol-EtOAc (2 : 1) furnished dengibsin (2a); 0.06 g), crystallised from MeOH-CHCl₃ (9 : 1), m.p. 227°. With Ac₂O/py it formed the diacetate (2b), crystallised from MeOH-CHCl₃ (9 : 1), m.p. 196°.

Chromatography of the neutral fraction as above afforded further amounts of ayapin (0.1 g) and aesculatin dimethyl ether (0.05 g).

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of Iron in Titanium Base Alloys using 4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol and a Long Chain Quaternary Ammonium Salt

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LITERATURE reveals several highly sensitive spectrophotometric methods for the determination of iron based on the complex formation of iron with 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR)¹⁻⁶. However, as PAR forms complexes with many metal ions, the above procedures are less selective and find little application in the analysis of complex samples in the diversified matrix. In our investigations we have observed that iron(III)-PAR anionic complex can be quantitatively extracted using cetyl dimethyl benzyl ammonium cation as intensely red coloured ion-pair, in chloroform in the pH range 6-7.5. When EDTA is added after complex formation of iron(III) with PAR, the interference of many metal ions can be effectively suppressed without causing any error in the determination of iron which has been exploited as a selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of iron in titanium alloys.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. Absorbance measurements were made with a Systronics 105 MK(II) spectrophotometer.

General extraction procedure: To an aliquot of the sample containing 1-40 µg ml⁻¹ of iron were added 1 × 10⁻³ M PAR (2 ml), 1 × 10⁻³ M EDTA (5 ml), 2 × 10⁻³ M CDBA (2 ml) and phosphate buffer (pH 6.7; 5 ml) solutions in sequence. The total volume was made up to 20 ml with